

M2.2 CS IP, SIP, AIP, DIP, SIARD,
geo-spatial data and ERMS
Specification update

E-ARK4ALL
REPORT

Table of Contents

Introductory remarks	6
Updated specifications	6
Common Specification for information Packages (CSIP)	6
E-ARK SIP	6
LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 2 SIP.pdf.....	6
E-ARK AIP	6
LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 3 AIP.pdf.....	6
E-ARK DIP	6
Common Specification for Electronic Records Management Systems	6
LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 5 CS ERMS.pdf.....	6
Common Specification for Geospatial data.....	6
LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 6 CS Geo.pdf.....	6
Common Specification SIARD	6
LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 7 SIARD.pdf	6
SIARD format 2.1 (English).....	7
SIARD format 2.1 (German).....	7

Introductory remarks

Within E-ARK4ALL, a significant amount of work has been undertaken updating the specifications originally produced as part of the E-ARK Project. The definitive versions of the specifications, which run to hundreds of pages, are maintained on-line in order to make them as accessible as possible to the widest cross-section of our target audiences.

For reporting purposes, links to the documents are given below, and full pdf versions are provided as free-standing appendices to this report.

Updated specifications

Common Specification for information Packages (CSIP)

<https://github.com/DILCISBoard/E-ARK-CSIP/blob/gh-pages/pdf/eark-csip.pdf>

Given here as:

LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 1 CS IP.pdf

E-ARK SIP

<https://github.com/DILCISBoard/E-ARK-SIP/blob/gh-pages/pdf/eark-sip.pdf>

Given here as:

LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 2 SIP.pdf

E-ARK AIP

<https://github.com/DILCISBoard/E-ARK-AIP/blob/gh-pages/pdf/aip-specification.pdf>

Given here as:

LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 3 AIP.pdf

E-ARK DIP

<https://github.com/DILCISBoard/E-ARK-DIP/blob/gh-pages/pdf/eark-dip.pdf>

Given here as:

LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 4 DIP.pdf

Common Specification for Electronic Records Management Systems

https://github.com/DILCISBoard/E-ARK-ERMS/blob/master/Specification/CSERMS_v2.0.0.pdf

Given here as:

LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 5 CS ERMS.pdf

Common Specification for Geospatial data

https://github.com/DILCISBoard/E-ARK-Geodata/blob/master/Specification/CSGeo_v2.0.0.pdf

Given here as:

LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 6 CS Geo.pdf

Common Specification SIARD

More work is going to occur with SIARD. Comments have been gathered during the

review: <https://github.com/DILCISBoard/SIARD/issues?utf8=%E2%9C%93&q=is%3Aissue+label%3A%22Review+comment%22+>

Given here as:

LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 7 SIARD.pdf

SIARD format 2.1 (English)

https://github.com/DILCISBoard/SIARD/blob/master/specification/2018-12-04_SIARD_Format_Version-2_1-English.pdf

Given here as:

LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 8 SIARD 2.1 eng.pdf

SIARD format 2.1 (German)

https://github.com/DILCISBoard/SIARD/blob/master/specification/2018-12-04_SIARD_Foramt_Version-2_1-German.pdf

Given here as:

LC-00921441 CEF-TC-2018-15 eArchiving M2.2 Appendix 9 SIARD 2.1 ger.pdf